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**Acute toxicity of Dolerite traces on *Catla catla* in Morga and Sarbhoka
Dam, Koriya district of Chhattisgarh**

Manju Rahi¹ and R.K. Singh²

Department of Zoology, Dr. C.V. Raman University, Kargi Road Kota, Bilaspur 495113

(C.G.)

Email: manjurahi89@gmail.com

The present study was undertaken to assess safety and efficacy of dolerite traces on fingerlings of *Catla catla*. Fingerlings of an average weight (10-15 gm) and average length 6-8 cm. were selected from the stock and kept for laboratory condition in aquarium of size 60x30x30 cm with 30 L. capacity for one month. After acclimatization *Catla catla* fish (n=6) were exposed to dolerite concentration for 15 and 30 days. Fingerlings in each group contains six were given graded doses of dolerite salt. First group received normal water (Tap water) as a control. The fingerlings were then maintained and observed daily for 15 days and 30days for further any toxicity. The numbers of survival were noted. Complete postmortem was done on all survivor or if any fingerlings found dead or moribund condition during the study period. Histopathological examination was performed on all collected tissues of individual fingerlings. Results will be discussed during the conference.